

Feminism : A Historical Review

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The term feminism comes from the Latin word *femina* meaning women. According to Rashmi Talwar "It was Alice Rossi an American who discussed its usage in a book review published in the *Athenaeum* on April 27, 1895. Ever since the word and the subject have been widely used. Rowbotham writes- The word feminist was invented by a French socialist Charles Fourier, in the early 19th Century. He imagined a new woman who would both transform and be herself transformed by a society based on association and mutuality rather than on competition and profits. His views influenced many women and combined self-emancipation and social emancipation changing one self was part of changing the world.¹

However from fifteenth century women's voices were beginning to be heard, and the first women to write about the rights and duties of her sex seems to have been the French woman Christine de Pisan (1364-1430). From the point of view of feminist political theory, what is interesting about the earliest writings is not so much the details of what individual writers of the time had to say, for these did not yet constitute an analysis of power relations or any kind of political programme, but rather the fact that debates over women's role in society that include a recognizably feminist perspective goes back further than had been commonly assumed.

It is also interesting to note that from the first such debates has an international character so that, for example, Christine de Pisan's influence can be traced to the debates in England at the end of seventeenth century.² "The first sizable wave of British secular feminist protest has been seen by Ferguson in this period. When for the first time significant numbers of women challenged received ideas about their sex in Pamphlets and in books.³ These Pamphlets and books were written by the then best known dramatists Aphra Benn (1640-89) and Marry Astell (1666-1731), who was recently been described as the first English feminist.⁴

Politically, the seventeenth century was of course of traditional authority and the events of civil war and interregnum would necessarily politicize many women as well as men. There is the evidence of women demonstrating, rioting and petitioning the Parliament. Even more dramatically, a number of the radical religious sects that sprang up challenged received notions as to appropriate sexual roles and behaviour: for example the Ranters preached extreme sexual permissiveness while Quakers argued that men and women were not only equal in God's eye but were equally eligible for the ministry.⁵

Functional domain of authority in the state and family was the question of equal importance during this period. Conservatives, who were defenders of absolute monarchical power used the analogy of the Father-Son relation to justify the king's rule over his people and went to the extent saying that it was sanctioned by the God. Thus patriarchy in the home was used as justification for parallel power in the state. Hobbes and Locke, the eminent political theorist of the time examined the relationships within family at some length, they fell back on arguments of social convenience and men's Superior strength to justify the continued subordination of women.

Some recent theorists have opined that, despite their universalistic pretensions, the basic premises of these early liberal writers are inherently biased against women. So it is argued that they are based on erratically male view of human nature that ignores human interdependence and attributes such as nurturing that have traditionally been associated with women.⁶ It is further claimed that the whole theory is predicated upon a distinction between the

public and private which involves the exclusion of women from the former and a devaluation of Latter.⁷

The middle years of the eighteenth century seem to represent a retreat from feminism, as arguments for women's rationality became less fashionable than belief in their innate weakness and dependence on men, the ideas of Astell and her contemporaries fell into disrepute and the very names of these early feminists were forgotten. The Age of Enlightenment was characterized by secular intellectual reasoning and a flowering of philosophical writing. The most important writer of the time was Mary Wollstonecraft, who is characterized as first feminist writer. Her fame extended across two continents. A *Vindication of Rights of Women* (1792), was written in response to Gouges' "Declaration of the Right of Women (1790)" is one of the first works that can be unambiguously be called feminist.

Evans has described the *Vindication of Rights of Women* as really an educational tract.⁸ Here she refutes the ideas of Rousseau who, in his celebrated work *Emile*, had included a Chapter on the very different educations of 'Sophy', Emile's future wife. Rousseau considered natures and abilities of men and women to be different. These biological differences defined their roles in the society with men becoming citizens and women, wives and mothers. Thus education of boys and girls must both recognize natural differences in ability and inclination "little girls always dislike learning to read and write, but they are always ready to learn to sew."⁹

Rousseau's view on women enraged Mary Wollstonecraft. Mary Wollstonecraft did not accept the notion that women were less capable of reason than men, or that vanity, weakness and Frivolity were the natural attributes of her sex. She went to the extent criticizing Rousseau that "I have, probably, had an opportunity of observing more girls in their infancy than JJ Rousseau" Wollstonecraft did not expect that education and freedom of choice would lead most women to reject their traditional role, but argued that they would enable them to perform it better. She did not expect the public/private distinction rather she sought to evaluate women's domestic responsibilities.¹⁰

The problem with this notion is that in a world in which domestic duties are unpaid, the economic dependence of a women upon her husband remains, Wollstonecraft had perceived the dangers of this but undermined its implication. Her insistence that motherhood is a form of citizenship does not solve the problem the male monopoly of formal political and legal power, which leave women dependent on men. Marx and Engels dubbed, those who believed that competitive capitalist society should be replaced with a more equitably organized, co-operative and rational by the means of neither conflict nor revolution but by the reform, as Utopian. The best known of these early socialists were St. Simon and Fourier. The feminist aspects of their thought were developed by their followers and attracted widespread interest and excitement in America as well as England. There was lively debate in the Press and on the public platform with lecture tours by prominent feminists requiring extensive policing.¹¹

Like family and sexuality, the division of labour, socialist theory never matched by community practice. Fourier's views were radical on this issue as he demanded a complete abolition to all specialization and the entire division of labour. He argued that the work could be fulfilling and creative only if it were chosen freely and an ideal community must be organized to allow all individuals to move freely from one occupation to another. He did seem to think that some jobs will naturally be more attractive to women and implied that they should care for very small children, but he also insisted that in any occupation at least some of the workers should be of the sex that does not perform it.¹² This implies that no man or women would be bound to one task for life and that domestic tasks like all other work would be the willingly performed expression of creativity rather than mindless drudgery.

Fourier's conceptions of freedom related to the work could not gain momentum and the responsibility for domestic life remained firmly with the women in all the communities. This was considered as a sign of women's political backwardness but as Barbara Taylor has argued 'it has less to do with any innate Partiality for individual wash-tubs than a fear, often justified, of becoming embroiled in a hard life over which they would have too little control and in which they would bear the brunt of utopian impracticality.¹³

The utopian socialists did not achieve their objectives and they have been viewed as an eccentric footnote to the history books. However the ideas of utopian socialists represent an important if brief alliance of liberal, socialists and feminists ideas which challenged the distinction between the private and the public and saw the interconnection between legal, political, economic and personal subordination. For the next 150 years, liberal campaigns for political and legal rights were largely separate from socialists preoccupations with the class struggle, while the idea of personal oppression frequently disappeared from the agenda; it is only in the work of some modern feminists that these separate strands are being drawn together again.

Liberal feminist theory is a traditional theory which finds its emergence from liberalism and seeks to adopt the liberal principles of liberty, equality and justice to women, without questioning the male power Mary Wollstonecraft's book, A Vindication of the Right's of women, John Stuart Mill's. The subjection of women, Harriet Taylor's Enfranchisement of women and Betty Friedan's The Feminine mystique and the second stage belong to this school. These feminists are visionary architects of liberal feminism who combine feminist ideals with humanist tenets, in other words gender justice based on humanism. It views sexism as dysfunctional because it deprives society of one half of its creative work force.¹⁴

The presumption that women belong to the family under the aegis of their husband had been central to male liberal theorists. Several scholars have pointed out that Locke's theory necessitates conjugal subordination of women as it is rooted in the concept of private property. The individual who form a social contract for the protection of their lives, their fortunes and their property are in Locke's and subsequent liberal theorists view male heads of households. Feminist theorist in natural right tradition sought to argue, however, that women were citizens, were 'persons' entitled to the same basic rights as men.

Because women were so rooted in the home, however and subject to male authority therein, it was difficult for even liberal theorist to avoid a critique of the home that had more radical implications than a limited liberal position. According to Josephine Donovan, the Enlightenment liberal feminists shared the following basic tenets.

1. A faith in rationality with some thinkers, such as Wollstonecraft. Reason and God are nearly synonymous with feminists such as Frances Wright and Sarah Grimke, the individual conscience is regarded as a more reliable source of truth than any established institution or tradition.
2. A belief that women's and men's souls and rational faculties are same.
3. A belief in education- especially training in critical thinking- as the most effective means to effect social change and transform society.
4. A view of the individual as isolated being, who seeks the truth apart from others. Who operates as a rational, independent agent, and whose dignity depends on such independence.

Finally, Enlightenment theorists subscribed to the natural rights doctrine, and while the most important theorists did not limit themselves to demanding political rights, the main stream of the 19th century women's movement settled upon these demands, in particular the demand for the vote.¹⁵

Elizabeth Cady Stanton first developed her ideas in the context of the movement for moral reform that had emerged from religious revivalism of the early years of the century. This led to the demands for the reform of divorce and child custody laws for women to have the access to education and employment that would give them economic independence and by the 1840, to the first organized political campaign for a married women's right to her own property. Ultimately Seneca falls convention of 1848, which Stanton. Later claimed represented the inauguration of a rebellion such as the world had never seen.¹⁶

Discussion of the feminist thinking in the mid nineteenth century has tended to concentrate on the writings of John Stuart Mill, who has been described as the only major liberal political philosopher to have set out explicitly to apply the principles of liberalism to women.¹⁷ Mill claimed that his political readings had always convinced him of the need to give women equal rights; However it was his close relationship with Harriet Taylor, whom he married in 1851 after the death of her husband, that gave an urgency to that intellectual conviction, and inspired his most famous feminists work. The subjection of women, it was embraced all over the world except Britain. It is difficult to exaggerate the enormous impression which it made on the minds of educated women all over the world.¹⁸

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